

Structure

- **1. Surveys:** Files post fixed with “survey” contain the pre- and post-forms used to collect data for the study
- **2. Questionnaires:** Files post fixed with “questionnaire” contains the questionnaires used to collect data during the study
- **3. Figures:** Files post fixed with “dashboard” contains the layout of CommunityTapestry’s dashboards and walkthrough
- **User Study.pdf:** script used in the study

1. Surveys

- **1. Pre-Study survey:** a survey used to collect demographic information from participants before the study, and information related to their project.
- **2. Post-Study survey:** a survey used to collect information from participants after the study.

2. Questionnaire

- **1. Contributor retention Dashboard Questionnaire:** a questionnaire used to collect information from the participants about the information presented in the contributor retention trends dashboard.
- **2. Communication Dashboard Questionnaire:** a questionnaire used to collect information from the participants about the information presented in the communication dashboard.
- **3. Types of contributions Dashboard Questionnaire:** a questionnaire used to collect information from the participants about the information presented in the types of contributions dashboard.

3. Figures

- **1. Contributor retention trend dashboard:** contains the visualization of the contributor retention dashboard from CommunityTapestry.
- **2. Communication by gender dashboard:** contains the visualization of the communication dashboard by gender from CommunityTapestry.
- **3. Types of contributors by affiliation dashboard:** contains the visualization of the types of contributions dashboard by affiliation from CommunityTapestry.
- **4. Walkthrough dashboard:** contains the visualization of the types of contributions dashboard used in the walkthrough.